

Complexes of 4-Amino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole with Cobalt(II), Rhodium(III), Nickel(II), Palladium(II), Zinc(II) and Cadmium(II)

P. D. SINGH, A. K. SINHA, K. K. ROY 'ANIL'
and

L. K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

*Manuscript received 18 October 1989,
accepted 3 September 1991*

THE present paper reports the preparation and characterisation of complexes of 4-amino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (AMTH) with Co^{II} , Rh^{III} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} .

Experimental

The ligand AMTH was prepared by the reported method¹. Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} chlorides were obtained from Johnson and Mathey.

$M(\text{AMT})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($n=0$ for $M=\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$, $n=2$ for Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} , and $n=4$ for Co^{II} and Ni^{II}): A methanolic solution (60–70 ml) of the ligand (0.002 mol) was added slowly with constant stirring to an aqueous methanolic solution of the appropriate hydrated metal(II) acetate or chloride (0.001 mol) and pH was raised to 6–7 by adding aqueous ammonia. It was refluxed for 2 h on a steam-bath and the resulting solid was washed with aqueous methanol and dried in a desiccator (CaCl_2).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found/(Calcd.)			Thermal loss (%) at 100° Found/(Calcd. for the loss of 2H ₂ O)	μ_{eff}^* B.M.	λ_{∞} $\Omega^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$
		M	N	Cl/Br			
[Co(AMT) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O	Buff colour	16.18 (16.32)	31.21 (31.02)	—	10.21 (9.98)	3.78	—
[Rh(AMT) ₂ Cl(H ₂ O)]	Light yellow	26.27 (26.48)	28.85 (28.82)	9.04 (9.12)	—	Dia.	—
[Ni(AMT) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O	Bluish green	16.13 (16.24)	29.88 (30.04)	—	10.18 (9.98)	3.40	—
[Pd(AMT) ₂]	Light yellow	31.75 (31.25)	32.29 (32.90)	—	—	Dia.	—
[Pd(AMT)(NH ₃)Cl]	Cream yellow	38.54 (38.70)	25.42 (25.46)	12.72 (12.89)	—	Dia.	—
[Zn(AMT) ₂].2H ₂ O	White	19.61 (19.71)	33.56 (33.78)	—	10.92 (10.86)	Dia.	—
[Cd(AMT) ₂].2H ₂ O	White	29.51 (29.69)	29.61 (29.58)	—	9.59 (9.51)	Dia.	—
[Co(AMTH) ₂ Cl ₂]	Dull red	16.16 (16.27)	30.81 (30.93)	19.58 (19.61)	—	4.82	14
[Ni(AMTH) ₂ Cl ₂]	Greenish blue	16.10 (16.22)	30.71 (30.95)	19.63 (19.61)	—	3.24	12
[Pd(AMTH)Cl ₂]	Light brown	36.40 (36.26)	19.10 (19.08)	24.00 (24.16)	—	Dia.	—
[Co(AMTH) ₂ (NO ₃)]NO ₃	Rose red	13.99 (14.07)	33.54 (33.42)	—	—	4.76	106
[Rh(AMTH) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	Orange yellow	23.18 (23.31)	25.40 (25.37)	24.12 (24.09)	—	Dia.	65
[Ni(AMTH) ₂ (NO ₃)]NO ₃	Bluish green	14.01 (14.02)	33.41 (33.44)	—	—	3.26	96
[Cd(AMTH)Br ₂]	Cream colour	28.61 (28.94)	14.56 (14.42)	40.92 (41.16)	—	Dia.	—

*At 301–303 K.

$M(\text{AMTH})_2X_2$ ($M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II} , and $X = \text{Cl}$ or NO_3), $\text{Pd}(\text{AMTH})\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Cd}(\text{AMTH})\text{Br}_2$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{AMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$: An ethanolic solution (60 ml) of the hydrated metal salt (0.001 mol) was refluxed with ethanolic solution of stoichiometric proportion of the ligand (at pH 2–3 in case of Rh^{III} and Pd^{II} and at pH 5–6 in case of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cd^{II}) for 2–3 h, when the complexes either separated slowly or on concentrating it to a small volume. The solid was washed with ethanol and dried in an air-oven (60–70°).

$[\text{Pd}(\text{AMT})(\text{NH}_3)\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{AMT})_2\text{Cl.H}_2\text{O}]$: The dichloro complex, $\text{Pd}(\text{AMTH})\text{Cl}_2$ or $[\text{Rh}(\text{AMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (~0.4 g) was suspended in 50% ethanol and refluxed with a few drops of ammonia for 2 h. The resulting solid washed with ethanol and dried as above.

Electrical conductivity, magnetic susceptibility, electronic absorption and reflectance spectra of the complexes were recorded as reported earlier². The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 421 and 577 and Beckman 800 spectrophotometers. The analytical and physical data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The ligand coordinates as a neutral ligand in acidic medium and formed acido complexes. In alkaline medium the ligand is deprotonated and

formed neutral inner complexes $M(\text{AMT})_2.n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}$, Ni , Zn , Cd or Pd and $n = 0, 2$ or 4), $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMT})(\text{NH}_3)\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{Rh}(\text{AMT})_2\text{Cl.H}_2\text{O}]$.

The complexes in general are insoluble in water but the acido complexes are slightly soluble in methanol, ethanol and dioxan. However, in DMF the neutral as well as the acido complexes are fairly soluble. The inner complexes $M(\text{AMT})_2.n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Pd}(\text{AMT})\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{AMT})_2\text{Cl.H}_2\text{O}$ show negligible electrical conductance values in DMF solution. In methanol, the complex nitrates $M(\text{AMTH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ ($M = \text{Co}$ or Ni) and $\text{Rh}(\text{AMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2\text{Cl}$ display molar conductance value in the range 65–106 $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating their 1 : 1 electrolyte nature³. The freshly prepared DMF solution of $M(\text{AMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ ($M = \text{Co}$ or Ni) shows conductance value of 12–14 $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating some solvation.

On heating, the neutral complexes $M(\text{AMT})_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Zn or Cd) become anhydrous below 120° indicating that H_2O may be uncoordinated in these complexes. The complexes $M(\text{AMT})_2.4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}$ or Ni) retain two water molecules at 150° indicating that at least the two water molecules may be coordinated to the metal ions while the other two are lattice water.

The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pd^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes are diamagnetic. The Ni^{II} complexes display magnetic moment value (3.24–3.40 B.M.) similar to octahedral or distorted octahedral nickel(II) complexes⁴.

The magnetic moment values of $\text{Co}(\text{AMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{AMTH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (4.76 and 4.82 B.M.) occur in the range of octahedral field⁴. The inner complex $\text{Co}(\text{AMT})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays anomalous magnetic moment value (3.78 B.M.) indicating spin-state equilibrium of Co^{II} ions⁵.

The solid reflectance spectra of $\text{Ni}(\text{AMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{AMTH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ display medium and broad bands located at 11 100–11 400, 15 150 and 23 000–25 000 cm^{-1} assignable to *d-d* transition in distorted octahedral (D_{4h} symmetry) field⁶. The solid reflectance spectra of $\text{Ni}(\text{AMT})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ display medium to weak bands at 11 500, 15 380, 19 600 and 27 030 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g^b$ and C–T bands in distorted octahedral field⁶. The reflectance bands of $\text{Co}(\text{AMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{AMTH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ observed at 17 850–18 690 and 20 000–20 830 cm^{-1} are similar to octahedral field and assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions⁷ respectively.

Ir spectra of the ligand display NH and NH_2 stretches at 3 280, 3 125, 3 130 cm^{-1} . The inner complexes display only one medium band at 3 125–3 250 cm^{-1} . The disappearance of major NH stretches and shifting of NH_2 stretch (3 280 cm^{-1}) to lower frequency suggest deprotonation of NH and bonding of NH_2 nitrogen to the metal atom. The hydrated complexes display a broad band at $3\,430 \pm 20$ cm^{-1} attributed to ν_{OH} of H_2O . The strong band at 1 600 cm^{-1} of the ligand molecule is attributed to the combination of triazole ring $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and δ_{NH_2} which splits into two bands in complexes at $1\,600 \pm 5$ and $1\,615 \pm 5$ cm^{-1} . The splitting of ir band at 1 600 cm^{-1} suggests bonding of NH_2 nitrogen in complexes. The ligand contains potential thioamide bands⁸ at 1 551, 1 335, 1 056 932 cm^{-1} ; the former three bands shift to higher wave numbers while band IV shifts to lower frequency in the complexes. In neutral complexes the thioamide band IV is observed at 710 ± 10 cm^{-1} , whereas in the diacido complexes $\text{M}(\text{AMTH})_2\text{X}_2$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$ or Ni and $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or NO_3), $[\text{Rh}(\text{AMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ and $\text{Pd}(\text{AMTH})\text{Cl}_2$, the thioamide band IV is observed in the range 840–885 cm^{-1} . A large shift of thioamide band IV attributed from $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ vibration suggests bonding of thioamide group by deprotonated thiol sulphur atom of the ligand molecule. The τ_{NH_2} of the free ligand is observed at 785 and τ_{NH} at 748 cm^{-1} . The former shifts to higher wavenumber in almost all the complexes. The latter band almost disappears in complexes containing deprotonated ligand but move slightly to lower frequency in the complexes containing neutral ligand. The new ir band observed at 450–480 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and at 360 ± 20 cm^{-1} to $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ vibrations⁹. Thus ir studies suggest bidentate (N, S) coordination of the ligand in these complexes. The Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes are suggested to possess distorted octahedral structure, the Pd^{II} square-planar and the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} tetrahedral.

References

1. H. BEYER and C. F. KROGER, *Ann.*, 1961, **637**, 135.

2. J. P. SRIVASTAVA, B. K. SINHA, R. SINGH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1797; B. N. KESHARI and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 272.
3. D. ATTANIO, I. COLLAMALI and C. ERCOLANI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 1537, 1541.
4. R. S. NYHOLM and B. N. FIGGIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 41; A. B. P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 763.
5. L. WILLIAMS, D. W. SMITH and R. C. STOUFFER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 590; R. C. STOUFFER, D. W. SMITH, H. A. CLVINGER and T. E. NORRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1167.
6. G. R. FRUBAKER and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **5**, 2114; R. A. D. WENTWORTH and T. S. PIPER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 709, 1524.
7. R. L. CARLINE in "Stereochemistry of Cobalt(II) Complexes in Transition Metal Chemistry", ed. R. L. CARLINE, 1965, Vol 1, p. 19.
8. I. SUZUKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1962, **35**, 1286, 1449, 1456; R. D. FEREMAN, D. M. BAIRD, I. BORDNER and J. DORFMAN, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 25; M. K. DAS, M. NATH and J. J. ZUCKERMAN, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **21**, 49.
9. M. GOLDSTEIN and W. D. UNSWORTH, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **4**, 342; D. M. ADAMS, "Metal-ligand and Related Vibrations", Arnold, London, 1967, p. 325; G. PEYRONEL, G. C. PELLACANI, A. PIGNEDOLI and G. BENETTI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 263.